

EVALUATION OF FAILED AND ABANDONED PROJECTS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR IN RIVERS STATE - A CASE OF THE RIVERS MONORAIL PROJECT.

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Abstract: *Nigeria, as a country, has a lot of failed and or abandoned projects in its public sector. This paper investigated the probable causes of project failure and abandonment in the public sector of Rivers state, with emphasis on the Rivers Monorail project and its consequent impact on society at large. Information was obtained mainly from personal interviews and a review of existing literature and journals. Literature, data, and information analysed showed that failure is said to occur in a component when the various elements that make up the component can no longer be relied upon to fulfil its initial objectives. On the other hand, abandonment is a situation whereby the client/owner of a project ceases to provide or make provisions for maintenance and operating services to a project. Abandonment occurs when management decides, for whatever reason best known to it to discontinue temporarily or permanently a project under development. It was concluded that the monorail project failed and was abandoned because of some issues around the contract that lead to the technical partner pulling out. There was also a change in government, cost overrun, delays, corruption and lack of technical know-how. It was recommended that for a project of such magnitude to succeed, proper contract must be in place with all parties understanding the terms and conditions. Also there need to be a detailed feasibility study, proper scope and plan, transparency on the side of the government and stakeholder's involvement.*

Keywords: *Abandonment, Failed, Project, Public, Sector*

1.1 Introduction

Projects in Rivers state and Nigeria are confronted with a lot of complexities and ambiguities as a result of uncertainties of not meeting project deadlines which also hinges on poor quality, cost overruns which invariably leads to failure and abandonment of such projects. Incessant failure and abandonment of projects by the public sector according to (Ubani and Ononuju, 2013); Olalusi and Otunola, 2012) are continuously posing serious challenges to the stakeholders in the built environment. The construction

industry is known to be the primary and focal point on which the development of any state or country rests on. It is viewed as the live wire as well as an instrument of choice of a State due to its role in providing the basic requirements for the entire citizenry. In as much as the industry remains the instrument of choice for most policy makers, the low performance of projects in the construction sector and the disillusionment ensuing there from by stakeholders seems to have become the rule and the exception in recent time.

To a greater extent, the growth and development of a state is determined by the quality and capability of its products from the built industry/ sector. Unfortunately, the inherent complex, uncertain and dynamic state of most construction projects created obvious problems of not achieving their initially stated objectives. Despite Rivers state's position as one of the largest economy in Nigeria compared to Lagos state, Rivers state has persistently performed poorly in terms of providing for her citizens the best life can offer in terms of better living standard, economic growth, justice and the likes (Ingwe, et al. 2010) Furthermore, Ingwe et al. (2010) opined that foregoing poverty indices has compelled the Rivers state government into developing infrastructural facilities as a means of propelling advocacy for rapid development in terms of stimulating economic growth and development, but the state government's performance in this regard has been dismal. The state's present and nearly ubiquitous collapse of various infrastructures like roads, railways, transport, and education are a pointer to these facts.

In Rivers state and Nigeria at large a lot of factors contributes to project failure which most often than not, leads to outright abandonment. Failure in construction projects is construed to be a negative consequence ensuing from risk actions that invariably leads to obstruction of any or some impending benefits derivable from the project. Furthermore, failure is said to occur in a component when the various elements that make up the components can no longer be relied upon to fulfil its initial objectives. On the other hand, abandonment is a situation whereby the client/owner of a project ceases to provide or make provisions for maintenance and operating services to a project. Abandonment occurs when management decides for whatever reason best known to it to discontinue temporarily or permanently a project under development (Ewusi-Mensah and Przasnyski, 1991).

Failed and abandoned construction projects abound everywhere; Malaysia, United States, Spain, Dubai, Saudi Arabia, Russia, Abu Dhabi (Hoe, 2013) and Nigeria (Ewa, 2013). According to Ewa (2013), there are about 4000 uncompleted or abandoned public projects to the tune of about ₦300 billion littered all over Nigeria and that it would take about 30 years to get them completed. Most authors have identified the factors responsible for construction project failure and abandonment. They include; lack of /poor planning, demise of client, unqualified project managers, incorrect cost estimates, poor design, political influence, poor funding etc. (Olalusi and Anthony 2012; Ubani and Ononuju 2013; Ayuba, et al. 2012; Hoe, 2013; Ayodele and Alabi 2011). Various scholars have tried to provide possible solutions

to curtail the incidences of failed and abandoned construction projects, but still the problem keeps on rearing its ugly head (Hoe, 2013; Olalusi and Anthony 2012; Ubani and Ononuju 2013; Ayuba, et al. 2012; Sahibzada and Mahmood 1992). The aforementioned authors tried to provide solutions to the problems of failed and abandoned construction projects by merely making suggestions in their studies which obviously have not yielded sufficient results. It is in the light of these assertions that this study would provide possible solutions/measures for containing construction project failure and abandonment by way of carrying out an in-depth study into unravelling measures that if not possible would curtail the excesses of such a menace.

2.0 The Rivers Monorail Project

The Rivers state monorail which is also known as the Rivers or Port Harcourt Monorail is a modern urban monorail transportation project located in Port Harcourt the Rivers state capital.

The Chibuike Rotimi Amaechi led administration felt it had a responsibility to plan for the present and future of the rivers people with a goal of repositioning Port Harcourt and the entire state as a major investment destination within the south south zone of Nigeria. To achieve this, you need a modern transport system to move people around within the shortest possible time. A monorail system fits this purpose. The monorail project will have both long- and short-term benefits to River's state. It will increase business activities within Port Harcourt city and will create a chain of businesses and jobs for the teeming public. The monorail will cement the State's place as Nigeria's Treasure base, a place of cultural advancement, a tourist attraction and a fully functional metropolis. The people of Rivers State can as a result look forward to an improved quality of life such as is enjoyed by members of many highly developed cities all over the world.

The Rivers state Government and TSI Property and Investments Holdings Limited signed an agreement on October 13, 2009 for the construction of the Rivers Monorail project in the city of Port Harcourt. Foundation laying ceremony was done on the 21st of July 2010 for the Rivers Monorail project to begin at the UTC Bus stop in Port Harcourt. The piling process was marked as a momentous occasion signifying as it does the beginning in earnest of one of possibly the most important and relevant constructions that has ever been embarked upon in the State, the country and even in Africa. The occasion was marked by the presence of representatives from the State Government, The Rivers Monorail Company, Senior Partners TSI Investments and Holdings and Technical Partners Intamin/Ponet. Progress on the implementation of the project by Rivers Monorail Company reached a stage where the Rivers State Ministry of Transport sought a suitably qualified, experienced, reputable international railway engineering consulting firm to review work done, make a detailed feasibility study and provide project management and technical support services to the Ministry of Transport. On March 1, 2011, the Ministry of Transport appointed Arcus GIBB to review the project, now under construction in Port Harcourt, and develop a business case for it. The investigation was completed December 2011.

On January 1, 2012, the Rivers State Government Ministry of Transport appointed Arcus GIBB as client representative/consultant to the Ministry of Transport for Phase 1A (Sharks Park to UTC Junction) of the project.

Route Description

The first phase of the Rivers Monorail project is the route from the Sharks Park area through Chief Lulu Briggs Road (formally Station Road) through Azikiwe Road and Aba Road past Garrison to Waterlines. A distance of 5.4km. On completion, the line will consist of a double track configuration, enabling trains to run in opposite directions, except at the terminals where there would be single tracks. Other routes contemplated are: Ikwerre road loop (Ikoku - UST Roundabout - Olu Obasanjo - Waterlines); Trans - Amadi loop (Garrison - Nkpogu/ Elakahia - Mother Cat - Ordinance Junction - Elakahia Housing Estate - Liberation Station- Air Force Junction – Waterlines).

3.0 Analysis of Failed and Abandoned Projects

The construction industry has been one of the critical sectors of Nigeria's economy before the era of the oil boom. Despite its role in the economy, it has been confronted with a lot of challenges as a result its inability to achieve ab initio set out goals. According to Ewa (2013), the issue of project failure and abandonment has been left unresolved for a very long time and this has created obvious room for a multiplier effect on the construction industry specifically and the entire economy as a whole. Olalusi and Anthony (2012) in their study opined that most construction projects that would have impacted on the economic and entire development of Nigeria, littered the nooks and crannies of the entire country. This affected the entire environment by defacing the aesthetics, and creating social problems as well as other health hazards to the entire populace.

The abandonment of a public sector construction project normally does not directly affect the entire populace as a result of its absorption by the government through reserved funds. This scenario often leads to a loss of opportunity by the public not being able to benefit from the intended purpose. On the other hand, should additional funds be made available to revive such projects, this would invariably incur extra opportunity cost of foregoing the project's original set objectives. (Hoe, 2013). According Onyekpere, (2011) the impact of failed projects in terms of cost and schedule overruns on a nation's economy is enormous as the new costs incurred as a result of these scenarios would have been deployed for the development of other important projects for the overall benefit of the entire citizenry. Most projects frequently fail to achieve their goals due to a myriad of problems ranging from imperfect project design, poor stakeholder management, delays between project identification and startup, delays during project implementation, cost overruns, and coordination failure. Amade et al (2014) opined that, the entire nooks and crannies in Nigeria is a washed with evidence of failed and abandoned construction projects stemming from cost related issues viz poorly articulated cost estimating principles, poor risk

management practices which is often hinges on clear cut knowledge of contingency provisions and management.

Latham, (1994) opined that the public sector is usually particular about using their spending power in obtaining value for money on a particular project while also assisting in enhancing the productivity and competitiveness of the construction industry in terms of obtaining better value for money generally in the long term. According to Potts, (2008), construction activities are prone to huge capital expenditure which the client may not commence implementation without confirming the state of the benefits accruing. In the case of the society benefiting from the project, in this case a public sector project, the justification for such a project will be based on the cost-benefit analysis. Much attention should be accorded to the budgetary process so that the project doesn't fail to achieve it stated objectives. Morris, (2012) further stated that managing public-sector projects can be more difficult than the private-sector projects because they most times operate in an environment that is prone to conflicts, while also involving different stakeholders with varied interests. While Ali, (2010) opined that the public sector are differentiated by the activities of their counterparts in the private sector.

There is no tendency for profit making, but rather a minute potential for income generation while also lacking on specific basis for performance measurement. Ali, (2010) further stated that the public sector organizations still possess the fulcrum to drive the growth of a nation's economy. According to KPMG (2011) government as well as public sector projects are uniquely positioned to deliver highly-tailored local solutions, based on key insights gained from previous work with similar public and private sector organizations in different parts of the world. A valuable mix of local specialists and leading global industry best practices consistently helps us to deliver valuable and sustainable strategies to the public sector clients. Possibly more than any other time in history, the public sector is confronted with a myriad of latest and complex challenges. Constant public scrutiny and the need for fiscal sustainability and a continued increase in demand for services has forced many governments to seek new ways to balance effective delivery of services in the short-term against long-term budget considerations. KPMG (2011) While Dlakwa and Culpin, (1990) opined that public sector projects in a developing country like Nigeria is prone to frequent delays compared to their counterparts in the private sector. The reasons for this are attributed to the delays in internal bureaucracy associated with most public service institutions.

According to Opawale, et al. (2013) a study carried out in year 2000 on infrastructural development revealed that before 1999, Nigeria was losing a whopping sum of about \$265 million annually via different types of illegal procedures in the award of contracts by government officials. These illegal practices were in the form of escalated contract sums, use of unqualified contractors, over-invoicing, awarding contracts without budgetary provisions and most importantly diversion of contract sums into private pockets which most often than not leads to the failure of such projects and subsequent

abandonment. Therefore it is the import of this work to critically provide far reaching solutions on how best incidences of failure and abandonment of construction projects could be curbed by specifically applying empirical research to address the underlying issues confronting public sector projects in Nigeria.

4.0 Review of Failed and Abandoned Projects – Rivers Monorail Project

The Monorail Project was to be completed in phases. The first phase that would run from Aggrey Road to Mile III by December 2013, the second phase will get to Waterlines by 2014.

The project which was a Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) Programme was expected to terminate at Eleme. Somewhere along the line, the core-investors pulled out and the entire project was threatened, but the Rivers State Government not wanting to fail on its campaign promises to the people decided to carry on. By 2014, monorail trains were performing test runs through UTC Station. In 2015, the Labour Party gubernatorial candidate Mr. Tonye Princewill said he would cancel the system if elected in 2015, Barrister Ezenwo Nyesom Wike the newly elected state governor announce that the project would be reviewed and in March of 2016 the project was reported abandoned by the state government. Again, in August of 2016 the yet uncompleted project was reported to have so far gulped \$400 million and cannot be compared with the fully operational 4.7 kilometres Moscow monorail that was also constructed by Intamin at a cost of \$240 million

Project failure the world over continues to be a talked about issue whose occurrence is at an alarming rate despite the increasing understanding of the concept of successful project management maturity and consistent stream of successful projects. According to Amponsah, (2012), statistics abound on failed projects and the testimony of such a scenario is a common phenomenon one could testify which is at par with widely reported cases of success. Belassi and Tukul (1996) opined that, a project that exceeds its completion due date, expenses overran its budget, or its outcomes did not satisfy its predetermined performance criteria, such a project is adjudged a failure. Failure in construction projects can be adduced to be a negative consequence emanating from perceived risk action which invariably results to obstruction of any or the entire benefits derivable from a project. Furthermore, Ayuba, et al. (2012) asserted that failure could be attributed to occur in a component when the individual components that make up the component can no longer be adjudged reliable in achieving its initial stated objectives.

In Nigeria, for instance, construction project failure has been attributed to a myriad of factors ranging from the use of poor quality materials, inexperienced personnel, (Ayuba, et al. 2012), unforeseen natural calamities, inaccurate cost and schedule estimate (Ubani and Ononuju, 2013), poorly designed feasibility studies; (Sahibzada and Mahmood, 1992) neglect of the significance of project planning processes; dearth of in executing complex projects; poor and unstable design; corruption and bribery; delay in making payments, etc (Nguyen and Chileshe, 2013); dearth of change management, poor

communication, inadequate resources, poorly defined requirements, poor risk management, (CSI, 2005).

Project abandonment on the other hand is seen as a consequence and implication of a failed project. Project failure and abandonment according to Ubani and Ononuju (2013) is described as the resultant effect of the consequence of reneging on an already commissioned project by virtue of the factors that precipitated the failure ab initio. Project abandonment on a general note, is the act of given up an action on an issue completely with the intention of not resuming either. When decisions on a project are put on hold without any specific time to commence work on the project, such a project is termed to be abandoned (Hanachor, 2012). Hanachor, (2012) further opined that there are two limits of schedule lag between suspension and resumption on a project. The short term lag ranges between 1 to 2 years, while the long term lag ranges between 3 to 5 years. Where the two scenarios are applied, a project is termed abandoned when some of the physical features are seen wearing away and becoming obsolete and out of use, which invariably would attract substantial amounts of funds to replace. According to Abdul Rahman, et al. (2013) a construction project is adjudged abandoned if it is not ready or completed for its occupants to use. While in the U.S., Malaysia, U.K. an abandoned construction project is one whose appearance shows some visible signs of distress such as deterioration, burned and possibly boarded up. Abdul Rahman, et al. (2013).

In Malaysia, the regulatory authorities (public) have laid down a set of conditions for adjudging a project as abandoned. The conditions include; one or more of the following ensues; no visible construction activities for a period of six months and beyond; the developer winds up; the constructor is unable to complete the project; the regulatory body declaring the project abandoned pursuant to Acts establishing it. According to Ayodele and Alabi, (2011), Nigeria has become the “world’s junk yard” of abandoned projects culminating into billions of naira. This assertion is hinged on the fact that a country enriched with a lot of potentials in the different endeavours of life and the construction industry in particular is bedeviled by the menace of project failure and abandonment.

A report according to Ayodele and Alabi, (2011) concluded that there are a lot of abandoned public sector projects to the tune of about 4000 which would require a whooping sum of over ₦300 billion naira and about 3 decades to complete. They further opined that the issue of project abandonment has been handled by the public authorities with kid gloves for quite some time and the consequence of this action is what we now see happening. The prevalence of failed and abandoned construction projects has been a burning issue and this calls for some concern among stakeholders in the built industry most specifically, clients and the public authorities. It is imperative to state that failed and abandoned projects have a debilitating impact on the aforementioned stakeholders.

Containing Public Sector Project Failure and Abandonment

Certain factors exist in order to facilitate the achievement of project objectives which in most cases are referred to as key performance indicators. While other researchers see this same factors as critical success factors (Saqib, et al. 2008; Baccarini and Collins 2003; Belassi and Tukel 1996; Adnan, et al. 2014; Jha and Iyer 2006). According to Saqib, et al. (2008), a study on project's success factors are most often than not considered as means of improving a project's effectiveness and efficiency there by eliminating totally any incidence of failure and abandonment. Baccarini and Collins (2003), opined that project success factors are generally a set of circumstances, events in the form of facts, influences that can contribute to the realization of a project's objective viz; cost, schedule, performance and stakeholders satisfaction. Furthermore, Pankaj and Bhangale, (2013) opined that success criteria as well as an individual's perception of success in the construction industry changes from one project to another with particular reference to the project's scope, size and the client's understanding of the design procedure, technological knowhow and a host of other factors. While on the other hand, factors' relating to success often develops not with a particular project, but across the industry as success is related to the perceptions and expectations of the client, consultant and contractors.

In the context of construction projects, the term success factors, according to Saqib, et al. (2008), are those factors predicting success on projects. While, Pankaj and Bhangale, (2013), see it as meeting or satisfying the expectations of the project's stakeholders as well as achieving the intended purpose of the project. If these aforementioned definitions of success factors are not deployed effectively in the course of executing a project, it is then evident that such a project would fail and subsequently be abandoned. Consequently, this work is intended to proffer solutions on how public sector projects failure and subsequent abandonment could be curtailed and contained with. In this study, we assume that any success factor for public sector project realization would invariably prevent such projects from failing and abandoned.

5 Conclusion

The effects of failed or abandoned projects include: stakeholders' disappointment, low living standard as a result of unemployment, wastage of scares government resources, economic activities of the state declined, and decrease in internally generated revenue of the state government. The rivers monorail project failed because it failed to meet schedule and cost Key Performance Indicators (KPI). The original technical partners withdrew indicating terms and conditions of the contract were not clear from the beginning. The state government kept going even without the technical knowhow. Secondly, original project was designed to cover 12 kilometres at a cost of N50 billion but the sum of N33.9 billion was spent on just 2.6 kilometres. It is declared abandoned after the present administration reviewed the design and contract papers and said this is not what River's people want at this time.

Recommendations

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Support from top management is a key to the successful execution of a project. The project manager and entire team members should try to see how they could get along with top management for purposes of getting support in terms of provision of adequate finance and logistics to support the project. Political risks should also be managed properly to avoid any devastating consequence on the project. A better way of handling this is to get acquainted with any change in political administration through good public relations.

Effective procurement process and procedures should be free, fair, and transparent. The best person for the job should be given the job based on competence and not through some other means that would be detrimental to the project later on. Provision of adequate finance is also vital. The client should make provision for funds to the project as at when due. And finally, information and communication management is one of the most vital factors for project success. The team members should follow clear cut channels of communication developed so that information on the project may not be lacking thus leading to success.

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